

PRO-COAST WP6 Preregistration

Psychological Drivers of Pro-Environmental Behaviour

Corrected version (25-06-2026)

This version has been corrected, because the original version had mistakes in the allocation of items to the Schwarz values construct Universalism (one item was incorrectly included and one was incorrectly omitted). This correction has been made after the examination of some data but without any examination of or analysis involving the Schwartz value items.

Research Focus

Understanding how human values, environmental emotions, social identity, awareness, and trust jointly explain:

- Willingness to sacrifice
- Environmental activism and identity
- Policy support

Utilised Variables

All item codes refer to the standard PRO-COAST questionnaire Wave 2 (which can be found signposted where this preregistration was signposted for reviewers). Variables described here but not used in hypotheses may be used for exploration, marked as such.

Items of theoretical interest

1. Human Values (Schwartz)

- Self-Direction: A1, A8
- Power: A2, A12
- Security: A4, A10
- Conformity: A5, A11
- Tradition: A7
- Benevolence: A9, A13
- Universalism: A3, A6

2. Awareness of Consequences

- A15, A16

3. Willingness to Sacrifice

- A17, A18

4. Community Identification

- A20, A22, A23
5. Environmental Self-Identity (in some contexts known as Environmental Citizenship)
- A24, A25
6. Environmental Activism
- A26, A27
7. Environmental Emotions
- Negative Emotions: B1–B4
 - Positive Emotions: B5, B6
8. Trust in Target Group:
- C1-C8 or alternatively C1-3, C8 (see discussion below)

Control covariates

9. Social Conservatism (F9, F16)
10. Gender (F1)
11. Education (F4)
12. Case Study Identity (different questionnaire implementations)

Hypotheses

H1: Value Conflict

- Universalism (A6, A14) will positively predict (a) Willingness to Sacrifice (A17, A18); (b) Environmental Self-Identity (A24, A25); (c) Activism (A26; A27); and (d) Awareness (A15; A16).
- Power (A2, A12) will negatively predict (e) Willingness to Sacrifice (A17, A18); (f) Environmental Self-identity (A24, A25); (g) Activism (A26; A27); and (h) Awareness (A15; A16).

H2: Self-Direction vs. Conformity

There will be:

- (a) a positive relationship between Self-Direction (A1, A8) and activism (A26, A27),
- (b) a negative relationship between Conformity (A5, A11) and activism (A26; A27).

H3: Emotion Effects

There will be:

- (a) a positive relationship between negative emotions (B1–B4) and activism (A26–A27),
- (b) a positive relationship between positive emotions (B5, B6) and willingness to sacrifice (A17, A18).

H4: Identity Moderation

- Environmental Self-Identity (A24, A25) will moderate the relationships between Universalism and (a) Willingness to Sacrifice (A17, A18); (b) Activism (A26; A27); and (c) Awareness (A15; A16), such that lower environmental identity weakens the positive effects of universalism.

H5: Trust Moderation

- (a) Trust (C1-3, C8) will moderate the relationship between negative emotions and Activism (A26; A27), such that lower trust strengthens the effect of negative emotions on activism.
- (b) Trust (C1-3, C8) will moderate the relationship between positive emotions and Willingness to Sacrifice (A17, A18), such that lower trust weakens the effect of positive emotions on willingness to sacrifice.

H6: Awareness Moderation

- Awareness of Consequences (A15, A16) will moderate the relationships between Universalism and (a) Willingness to Sacrifice (A17,A18); (b) Environmental Self-Identity (A24, A25); and (c) Activism (A26; A27), such that greater awareness strengthens the positive effect of universalism.

Analysis plan

Data preparation

Gender has been measured as multiple categories, but these will be collapsed to a binary variable non-man (woman, non-binary, other) vs man. For all other variables, responses are on ordinal scales, to be treated as continuous. All “Prefer not to say” responses will be set to missing. “Don’t know” (left-right ideology only) will be set to the neutral scale point (4).

Multi-item composites variables will be prepared as the mean of z-transformed individual items, thus they will be validly defined unless all items are missing. If composites with three or more items have a Cronbach’s $\alpha < 0.5$, items will be dropped in order of those giving the greatest increase to alpha until $\alpha \geq 0.5$ or only two items are left. Two-item composites will not be used if $r < 0.3$. For composites failing the minimum criteria (despite dropping), a single item will be used, the one with the greatest face validity, which will be judged by a researcher at the data-preparation stage without yet having constructed any models.

All variables will be standardised (z-transformed) prior to use in registered models.

Trust scale

At point of preregistration, the research team is discussing different theoretical perspectives on the conception of trust. We have defined two different trust scales – a broad one (C1-C8) which includes both the respondent's trust in another group and their perceptions of intra-group coherence within that group, and a narrower one focusing on inter-group trust without the additional dimension of perceptions of intra-group coherence within that group (C1-3, C8). All analyses involving that construct will be run with both scales. If results are the same with both scales, regarding confirmation or rejection of trust-related hypotheses, it will be up to the researchers' discretion which scale to report. If the results are different, the researchers will report both sets of results.

Model specification

Bayesian models will be constructed with the R package brms function `brm()`, with default arguments unless otherwise specified. The values block model formulae are as follows:

1. Sacrifice ~ Universalism * Identity + Universalism * Awareness + Power
2. Identity ~ Universalism * Awareness + Power
3. Activism ~ Universalism * Identity + Universalism * Awareness + Power + SelfDirection + Conformity
4. Awareness ~ Universalism * Identity + Power

The emotions block model formulae are as follows:

5. Sacrifice ~ PosEmotion * Trust
6. Activism ~ NegEmotion * Trust

In addition, each formula will contain a random intercept for case study, and (fixed and without interactions) the control covariates Social Conservatism, Gender, and Education.

Model implementation

If missingness in any control covariates reduces the number of complete cases by more than 5% of what would be non-missing without that covariate, that control covariate will be dropped. If multiple control covariates have this effect, the one that causes most data to be lost will be dropped first. After dropping one control variable, others will be dropped if they reduce the new number of complete cases by more than 5%. If a dependent variable has been reduced to a single item, "family = cumulative()" will be used to construct the model. Missingness in non-control variables causes data-dropping (there will be no imputation).

To confirm appropriate model fit, two diagnostic plots will be examined: residuals vs fitted values (scatterplot), and residuals vs group (boxplot) will be examined. Models will be adjusted as necessary (for example by modelling residual standard deviation as a function of case study if relevant heteroscedasticity is observed).

Effects will be regarded as discovered when the 95% credible interval for the coefficient posterior excludes zero. The credible interval and median will be reported.

In a second investigation, to investigate the generality of key effects, and to additionally control for the possibility that these effects differ across case studies, models will be repeated, with the fixed main effects of Universalism and Power (values block) and positive and negative emotions (emotions block) subject to random slopes by case study. From these models, the credible interval and median will be again reported for universalism, power, and

emotions, and the credible interval and median will be reported for the cross-case-study variation.

For all models, fixed beta priors will be normal($M = 0$, $SD = 0.2581$), with the SD derived from Pearson's r distribution across 322 meta-analyses of effect sizes across social psychology (Richard et al., 2003)¹. Random sigma priors will be Student's t ($M = 0.1221$, $scale = 0.0852$, $df = 4.1561$), which is the best-fitting Student's t for a dataset containing inter-study variation estimates from 360 meta-analyses of studies reporting Pearson's r from across the field of psychology (van Erp et al., 2017)². Calculations describing these derivations in full are at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20181224>. As a prior sensitivity analysis, we will also report robustness tests where we repeat the analyses with brm() default priors, which are entirely flat for fixed β , and very wide (and thus uninformative) for random σ (Student's t with mean 0, scale 2.5, and df 3).

Sample determination

Data collection is underway, but researchers have not accessed data at the point of preregistration. The data will be all data collected by the PRO-COAST consortium stakeholder survey Wave 2 up until 13:00 CET 2026-06-01. The anticipated sample size is somewhere between 600 and 900. If the sample is less than 600 at that point, or if any single case-study has produced less than 50 data points, data collection will be extended for exactly 7 days from the original deadline. There are no reasons for excluding data other than any listed above

Scope Note

The pre-registration focuses exclusively on H1–H6 as confirmatory hypotheses.

Additional analyses will be:

- Exploratory
- Clearly labelled
- Reported transparently

¹ Richard, F. D., Bond Jr, C. F., & Stokes-Zoota, J. J. (2003). One Hundred Years of Social Psychology Quantitatively Described [doi:10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331]. *Review of General Psychology*, 331-363. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331>

² van Erp, S., Verhagen, J., Grasman, R. P. P., & Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2017). Estimates of Between-Study Heterogeneity for 705 Meta-Analyses Reported in *Psychological Bulletin* From 1990–2013. *Journal of Open Psychology Data*. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jopd.33>